

Analysis of the Ecological State Of Rivers of the Ararat Water Basin Management Area Using Background Concentrations

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Abstract

The article argues that an inherent limitation of maximum permissible concentrations is their inability consider the specificities of the geographical areas. In this regard, the Water Framework Directive developed by the European Union has played an important role in shifting river water quality assessment in Armenia from assessing maximum permissible concentrations of hydrochemical parameters to a more comprehensive approach which based on natural background concentrations. This shift, in force since 2011, emphasizes the importance of ecological integrity and use of natural reference points at the rivers for water quality assessment. The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Armenia “On Establishing Water Quality Standards for Each Basin Authority” distinguishes five separate classes and the assessment of chemical water quality is based on the class with the least favourable quality indicator. Water quality classes of the Vedi, Arpa and Yeghegis rivers for the period 2013–2024 were studied based on the analysis of background concentrations. The analysis showed that in a river waters under study the background concentrations of suspended solids, chemical oxygen demand, ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions, as well as the following metals: manganese, molybdenum, aluminum, iron, barium and tin are exceeded.

Keywords: water quality, background concentration, river.Arpa, Vedi, Yeghegis, Armenia

1. INTRODUCTION

To assess the ecological state of rivers, complex indicators are used that allow quantitatively assessing water pollution simultaneously based on a wide range of quality indicators [1,2]. It should be noted that most of the complex characteristics of the state of water bodies developed to date are somehow related to the existing maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) [3], which were developed in the 20th century in the former USSR and were used to assess the pollution of water systems. It should be noted that MPC has the following shortcomings: it does not take into account the characteristics of the area, the same standards are applied to rivers flowing in different physical and geographical zones, and it does not take into account a natural background concentration of a pollutants in a water systems.

According to the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60 / EC), all European surface waters should be in good ecological condition after 2015, and water objects with poor quality water should be improved through targeted measures quality to a better status. Each EU Member State has developed classroom schemes for water quality classification according to WFD [4]. For example, in France, the SEQ-system is used for the classification of river water quality, consisting of three sections. To classify water quality, 15 descriptors are separated into 156 indicators, taking into account similar factors and effects. The evaluation is carried out using the boundary value table, which defines the boundaries of classes.

Then the index values are calculated based on which the water quality is classified into 5 classes based on the water useability. Germany's chemical quality classification scheme

consists of 4 main classes and 3 subclasses, with a similar biological classification. The grades obtained are mapped through color codes.

Water quality assessment in the Danube River Basin according to the EU WFD is carried out according to separate indicators [4]. In this classification scheme, indicators are classified into five classes. Class I is referred to as "reference" or background concentration; class II is a target value that should be followed; the III-V classes are part of the "non-executable" classification scheme and their values are usually 2-5 times higher than the target value [5].

According to the EU WFD Rural Water Quality Assessment, due to the lack of biological monitoring, assessment was made only with the use of water quality chemical indicators. Natural background concentrations of hydrochemical indices were taken into account. The determination of background concentrations according to the EU WFD was performed using a statistical method using the probability logarithmic distribution function. The expected background status of the reference state is the absence or insignificance of anthropogenic pressure. It is closely connected with background concentration (BC). BC is the value of the water quality indicator concentration before exposure to any source of pollution.

The calculations of the BC took place in the RA rivers in 2005-2010 hydrochemical monitoring. The Government of the Republic of Armenia, "Decree N75-N of 27 January 2011", establishes the surface water quality assessment system in Armenia for each parameter of the water quality for each water basin by the five class status: "excellent" (1st grade), "good" (2nd grade), "Average" (3rd grade), "unsatisfactory" (grade 4) and "bad" (5- class). The general assessment of the chemical quality of water is shaped by the class of the lowest quality indicator [6].

If the different indicators of the quality of the surface water object fall into different classes of quality, the final classification is considered the worst. The following principle applies: "If someone is in bad shape, then everyone is in a bad condition" or "one is out, everyone is out" principle.

The advantages of the new norms of water quality in Armenia are:

- The classification of environmental norms is based on the natural BCs.
- Selection of indicators was made taking into account the pressures on the surface water of the Republic of Armenia (mainly 43 parameters).
- Disclosure of real pressures on water quality.
- Detection of river basin pollutants.
- Established for 14 major river basins in Armenia.

The territory of the Republic of Armenia is divided into six surface water management basins:

1. Northern Water Basin Management Area,
2. Akhuryan Water Basin Management Area,
3. Hrazdan Water Basin Management Area,
4. Sevan Water Basin Management Area,
5. Ararat Water Basin Management Area,
6. Southern Water Basin Management Area.

The water quality of the rivers Hrazdan (Simonyan et al., 2020) and Achuryan (Simonyan et al., 2019), as well as the rivers of Lake Sevan and several reservoirs in Armenia (Simonyan, 2021) has been assessed using BC. This study aims to evaluate the water quality of the rivers of Ararat Water Basin Management Area: Vedi, Arpa and Yeghegis using BC.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Study area

Arpa River originates in north-west of Artsakh Plateau, at an altitude of 3200 m and flows into the Araks River, on the border of Nakhijevan and Turkey. The length of river is 126km (in Armenia 90km), basin – 2630 km². It flows through the gorges with a big difference in altitude. Mines and waterfalls are fallen into the river near the town Jermuk. Arpa valley is wide in some parts of average flow, the river flows through Araks plain in lower flow [42]. On the Arpa River are five monitoring point: number 83 - 0.5 km above the city of Jermuk, number 84-0.5 km above the city of Vayk, number 85-0.5 km below the city of Vayk, number 86-0.5 km above the city of Yeghegnadzor, number 87-0.5 km below the village Areni [1].

Vedi is a river in Armenia, a left tributary of the Araks River. The length is 58 km, the basin area is 633 km². It starts from the south-eastern slopes of the Mankan mountain range, about 2700 meters above the Geghama mountain range. In its upper reaches, the river is mountainous. The lower stream passes through the Ararat Valley and flows into the Araks, about 2 km south of the village of Yeghegnavan, at an altitude of 810 m above sea level. There are two monitoring points on the Vedi River: sampling points No. 80 - 0.5 km above Urtsadzor and No. 82 at the mouth of the river.

The length of the Yeghegis River is 49 km. It originates on the southern slope of Mount Vardenis (in the eastern part of the Vardenis Range), at an altitude of over 3,000 meters. The general direction of the flow is southwest. It flows into the Arpa near the city of Yeghegnadzor at an altitude of 1,059 m above sea level. There is one monitoring point on the Yeghegis River: No. 88 - 0.5 km below the village of Shatin.

2.2. Method of water quality classification

According to the Government of the Republic of Armenia's decision "On the Establishment of Water Quality Standards for Each Water Basin Management District," five classes are distinguished. Each class is designated by color (see Table 1): "excellent" (1st class - blue), "good" (2nd class - green), "average" (3rd class - yellow), "unsatisfactory" (4th class - brown) and "bad" (5th class - red). The overall assessment of the chemical quality of water is formed by the class of the lowest quality indicator. Thus, if different quality indicators of a surface water body fall into different quality classes, the final classification is considered to be the worst. The following principle is applied: "If someone is in bad shape, then everyone is in bad shape" or the principle "someone went out, everyone went out"

Table 1 - Water quality classification according to the EU WFD

Water quality class	Assessment	Water quality
1		Excellent
2		Good
3		Average
4		Unsatisfactory
5		Bad

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As noted at the introduction of this article, the MPC has the following shortcomings: the same standards are applied to rivers flowing in different physical and geographical zones and do not take into account the natural background content of pollutants in rivers.

Table 2 - Environmental standards for the quality of river water in the Arpa River basin

Quality parameters	MPC	Water quality class according to BC					Units
		I	II	III	IV	V	
COD	30	10	25	40	80	>80	mgO ₂ /L
NH ₄ ⁺	0.5	0.03	0.4	1.2	2.4	>2.4	mg/L
NO ₂ ⁻	0.08	0.016	0.06	0.12	0.3	>0.3	mgN/L
PO ₄ ⁻³	0.1	0.048	0.1	0.2	0.4	>0.4	mg/L
Suspended solids	10	12.8	15.3	25.5	51.0	>51.0	mg/L
Fe	0.1	0.036	0.072	0.5	1	>1	mg/L
Mn	10	6	12	24	48	>48	µg/L.
Ba	700	14	28	56	1000	>1000	µg/L.
Sn	0.112	0.04	0.08	0.16	0.32	>0.32	µg/L.

Table 2 shows the environmental standards for the quality of river water of some parameters in the Arpa River basin: MPC and BC. As can be seen in the Arpa River basin, MPC differs from BC (water quality class I) and generally exceeds BC.

Table 3 shows the water quality classes of the Arpa, Vedi and Yeghegis rivers for 2013-2024. The water quality data for the rivers according to BC are taken from the website “Hydrometeorology and Monitoring Center” SNCO of the Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Armenia (On the results of ecological monitoring of the environment of the Republic of Armenia. Bulletin. 2013-2024) [9].

The water quality in the area above the Urtsadzor village on the Vedi River (sampling point No. 80) was “good” (class 2) for the entire study period. In 2013 The water quality of the Vedi River in the lower part of the city of Ararat (sampling point No. 82) is “good” (class 2). In the period 2014-2017, the water quality at sampling point No. 82 is “average” (class 3) due to chemical oxygen demand(COD), ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions.

In 2018, the water quality of the Vedi River along the entire length of the river was assessed as “good” (class 2). In 2019, the water quality of the Vedi River below the city of Ararat is characterized as “poor” (class 5) due to suspended solids. In 2020, the water quality at sampling point No. 82 of the Vedi River improves and becomes “moderate” (class 3) due to the content of manganese, iron, aluminum and suspended solids. In the period 2021-2023, the water quality at sampling point No. 82 becomes “poor” (5 class) due to the content of iron and suspended solids, nitrite ion, manganese and aluminum. In 2024, the water quality in the area above the village of Urtsadzor on the Vedi River (sampling point No. 80) deteriorates from class 2 to class 3, while in sampling point No. 82 the water quality remains “poor” (class 5)

Table 3. Classification of Water quality of the Rivers Vedi, Arpa and Yeghegis based on the BC

Rivers	Vedi		Arpa					Yeghegis
Years	80	82	83	84	85	86	87	88
2013	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
2014	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
2015	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2016	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
2017	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2018	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2019	Green	Red	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2020	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2021	Green	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Orange	Orange
2022	Green	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Orange

2023								
2024								

The water quality in the area above the village of Urtsadzor on the Vedi River (sampling point No. 80) was “good” (class 2) for the entire study period. In 2013 The water quality of the Vedi River in the lower part of the city of Ararat (sampling point No. 82) is “good” (class 2). In the period 2014-2017, the water quality at sampling point No. 82 is “average” (class 3) due to COD, ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions.

In 2018, the water quality of the Vedi River along the entire length of the river was assessed as “good” (class 2). In 2019, the water quality of the Vedi River below the city of Ararat is characterized as “poor” (class 5) due to suspended solids. In 2020, the water quality at sampling point No. 82 of the Vedi River improves and becomes “moderate” (class 3) due to the content of manganese, iron, aluminum and suspended solids. In the period 2021-2023, the water quality at sampling point No. 82 becomes “poor” (5 class) due to the content of iron and suspended matter, nitrite ion, manganese and aluminum. In 2024, the water quality in the area above the village of Urtsadzor on the Vedi River (sampling point No. 80) deteriorates from class 2 to class 3, while in sampling point No. 82 the water quality remains “poor” (class 5)

In 2013, 2014 and 2016, the water quality of the Arpa River along its entire length was "good" (class 2) quality. 2015 in the sections of the Arpa River above Jermuk and above Vayk, the water was of "good" quality (class 2), and in the sections below Vayk, above Yeghegnadzor and below Areni, it was of "average" quality (class 3) due to molybdenum. And in 2017 in the sections of the Arpa River above Jermuk, above Vayk, above Yeghegnadzor and below Areni, the water was of "average" quality (class 3), and in the section below Vayk, it was of "unsatisfactory" quality (class 4).

The water quality of the Arpa River in 2018 in the sections above Jermuk, above and below Vayk, above Yeghegnadzor and below Areni was assessed as "average" (class 3) for the content of molybdenum, iron, and barium. In 2019 and 2020, the water quality of the Arpa River above the city of Jermuk was assessed as "good" (class 2), above and below the city of Vayk, above the city of Yeghegnadzor and below the village of Areni was assessed as "average" (class 3) for the content of molybdenum, manganese, iron, barium, tin and suspended solids. The water quality of the Arpa River in 2021 above the city of Jermuk, above and below the city of Vayk was assessed as "average" (class 3). Above the city of Jermuk - for the content of iron, above the city of Vayk - for the content of molybdenum, manganese and iron, below the city of Vayk - for the content of molybdenum, iron, barium and tin. In the areas above the city of Yeghegnadzor and below the village of Areni, the water quality was assessed as "unsatisfactory" (class 4) for the content of molybdenum. In 2022, the water quality of the Arpa River in areas above the city of Jermuk, above and below the city of Vayk, above the city of Yeghegnadzor and below the village of Areni was assessed as “average” (class 3): above the city of Jermuk for ammonium ions, iron and suspended matter, above the city of Vayk for iron and aluminum, below the city of Vayk for iron, above the city of Yeghegnadzor for molybdenum and iron, below the village of Areni for molybdenum, iron and barium. In 2023, the Water Quality of the Arpa River was also assessed as “average” (class 3) in the areas above the city of Jermuk, above and below the city of Vayk, and as “unsatisfactory” (class 4) above the city of Yeghegnadzor and below the village of Areni: above the city of Jermuk for ammonium ions, iron and suspended solids, above the city of Vayk for iron and aluminum, below the city of Vayk for iron, above the city of Yeghegnadzor for molybdenum and iron, below the village of Areni for molybdenum, iron and barium. And in 2024, the water quality of the Arpa River along its entire length is “average” (class 3) quality.

In 2013, 2014 and 2016, the water quality of the Yeghegis River in the lower part of the village of Shatin (sampling point No. 88) was “good” (class 2). In 2015 and in the period 2017-

2020, at sampling points No. 88, the water quality was “moderate” (class 3) due to molybdenum, iron and suspended matter, and in 2020, also due to barium and aluminum. Starting in 2021, the water quality of the river has deteriorated - “unsatisfactory” (class 4) due to molybdenum ions.

Finally, table 3 shows that the deterioration of water quality in the Vedi and Yeghegis rivers has been observed since 2020.

4. CONCLUSION

Thus, it has been shown that when assessing the quality of river water in Armenia, instead of maximum permissible concentrations of chemical water quality parameters, natural background concentrations are used in accordance with the EU WFD and, according to the Decree of the Government of the Republic of Armenia "On the establishment of water quality standards for each basin management area", five classes are distinguished. Each class is designated by color: "excellent" (1st class - blue), "good" (2nd class - green), "average" (3rd class - yellow), "unsatisfactory" (4th class - brown) and "poor" (5th class - red). The overall assessment of the chemical quality of water is formed according to the class of the lowest quality indicator.

The analysis showed that in the waters of the Vedi, Arpa and Yeghegis rivers for the period 2013–2024, BC of manganese, molybdenum, iron, aluminum, barium and tin were exceeded. suspended solids, COD and ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions

It is shown that deterioration of water quality in the Vedi, Arpa and Yeghegis rivers has been observed since 2020, especially in monitoring points 82, 86, 87 and 88

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